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3 **Widespread occurrence of dissolved oxygen anomalies, aerobic microbes,**
4 **and oxygen-producing metabolic pathways in apparently anoxic ecosystems**
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17 **Abstract**

18 Nearly all molecular oxygen (O₂) on Earth is produced via oxygenic photosynthesis by plants or
19 photosynthetically active microorganisms. Light-independent O₂ production, which occurs both
20 abiotically, e.g., through water radiolysis, or biotically, e.g., through the dismutation of nitric oxide
21 or chlorite, has been thought to be negligible to the Earth system. However, recent work indicates
22 that O₂ is produced and consumed in dark and apparently anoxic environments at a much larger
23 scale than assumed. Studies have shown that isotopically light O₂ can accumulate in old
24 groundwaters; that strictly aerobic microorganisms are present in many apparently anoxic habitats;
25 and that microbes and metabolisms that can produce O₂ without light are widespread and abundant
26 in diverse ecosystems. Analysis of published metagenomic data reveals that the enzyme putatively
27 capable of nitric oxide dismutation (Nod) forms four major phylogenetic clusters and occurs in at
28 least 16 bacterial phyla most notably the *Bacteroidota*. Similarly, re-analysis of published isotopic
29 signatures of dissolved O₂ in groundwater suggests in-situ production in up to half of the studied
30 ecosystems. Geochemical and microbiological data supports the conclusion that “dark oxygen”
31 production is an important and widespread yet overlooked process in apparently anoxic
32 environments with far-reaching implications for subsurface biogeochemistry and ecology.

33 **Principles of light-independent oxygen production and consumption**

34 By far the most important source of molecular oxygen (O₂) on Earth is photosynthesis, a biotic
35 process that generates O₂ as a byproduct through the lysis of water molecules (Nelson and Ben-
36 Shem 2004; Fischer, Hemp and Johnson 2016). Despite the quantitative importance of
37 photosynthesis, O₂ is additionally produced by light-independent abiotic and biotic reactions.
38 Here, we refer to all light-independent production pathways, whether biotic or abiotic, as “dark
39 oxygen” production (DOP; **Fig. 1**).

40 Abiotic DOP specifically proceeds via the radiolysis of water (Gutsalo 1971; Das 2013),
41 which is driven in dark geological systems such as aquifers and bedrock by the decay of radioactive
42 elements present in surrounding rock, and via the oxidation of surface-bound radicals on Si-
43 bearing minerals such as quartz (He *et al.* 2021, 2023; Stone *et al.* 2022). Although direct O₂
44 formation is likely negligible (Le Caër 2011), both pathways produce abundant reactive oxygen
45 species (ROS) such as hydroxyl radical (OH[•]), superoxide (O₂^{•-}), and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂).
46 ROS can be subsequently disproportionated biotically by the enzymes superoxide dismutase and
47 catalase—or abiotically by ferrous iron and other reduced metals—to form O₂ and H₂O (Xu *et al.*
48 2013; Sutherland, Hemingway and Johnston 2022). However, surface-bound radical generation
49 requires either intense mechanical abrasion (He *et al.* 2021, 2023) or hydrothermal temperatures
50 (Stone *et al.* 2022). Thus, while possibly important earlier in Earth’s history, this mechanism is
51 likely insignificant in most low-temperature, anoxic systems today. In contrast, water radiolysis
52 followed by ROS disproportionation can act as a net source of O₂ to groundwater systems over
53 geologic timescales (i.e., the timescale of radioactive decay).

54 Biotic DOP is carried out by microorganisms belonging to several different and mostly
55 well-known lineages within the *Archaea* and *Bacteria*. Microbial DOP proceeds via three
56 fundamentally different microbial processes: chlorite (ClO₂⁻) dismutation (Xu and Logan 2003),
57 nitric oxide (NO) dismutation (Ettwig *et al.* 2012), and the lysis of water via methanobactins
58 (Dershwitz *et al.* 2021). Despite this breadth of microbial metabolisms producing O₂, these
59 processes were all reported relatively recently: chlorite dismutation in the mid 1990’s (van Ginkel
60 *et al.* 1996), nitric oxide dismutation in 2010 (Ettwig *et al.* 2010), and water lysis by
61 methanobactins only in the past three years (Dershwitz *et al.* 2021). In both dismutation pathways,
62 the crucial O₂-producing step is the electron-neutral dismutation of ClO₂⁻ or NO into O₂ and
63 chloride (Cl⁻) or O₂ and dinitrogen gas (N₂) or nitrous oxide (N₂O). Chlorite dismutase and
64 proposed nitric oxide dismutase enzymes are both heme-containing oxidoreductases (Hofbauer *et al.*
65 2014; Murali, Hemp and Gennis 2022), yet they are unrelated and belong to distant protein
66 families. In contrast, the molecular mechanism for methanobactin-dependent lysis of water
67 remains unclear to date (Dershwitz *et al.* 2021) and, unlike for both dismutation pathways, the
68 boundary conditions for the energetic feasibility of methanobactin-dependent water lysis do not
69 suggest a significant occurrence in natural ecosystems.

70 Balancing the O₂ sources, the most important sink for O₂ is respiration. Because the
71 reduction of O₂ provides the largest free energy release per electron transfer with the exception of
72 fluorine and chlorine, it is a powerful electron acceptor (Catling *et al.* 2005; Jørgensen 2006).

73 Aerobic respiration is therefore widespread in the tree of life; many single-celled eukaryotes
 74 (Zimorski *et al.* 2019), ~70 % of bacteria (Morris and Schmidt 2013), and essentially all
 75 macroscopic life forms respire O₂ (Hedges *et al.* 2004). However, in recent years, it is becoming
 76 increasingly recognized that many aerobes occur in ecosystems in which O₂ does not seem to be
 77 available or at least does not accumulate. For example, strictly aerobic methanotrophs are reported
 78 to be active in apparently anoxic sediments of hydrocarbon seeps (Ruff 2020) and wetlands (Reis
 79 *et al.* 2024). The presence of aerobes in such environments has historically been explained either
 80 by: (i) their capability to exist in a facultative anaerobic lifestyle, (ii) their capability to remain
 81 dormant during unfavorable conditions, or (iii) small amounts of oxygen that become available
 82 through advection, storage, or diffusion, or that are produced via photosynthesis. Indeed, recently
 83 developed dissolved O₂ sensors reveal that nanomolar (i.e., ~10⁻⁹ mol L⁻¹) concentrations of O₂ are
 84 common in nature, leading to the presence of nanoaerobic microbes in many apparently anoxic
 85 environments (Berg *et al.* 2022). In this review, we compile and provide evidence for a fourth,
 86 largely overlooked mechanism by which (nano)aerobic microbes can survive in apparently anoxic
 87 environments even when sunlight is not available, advection is not present, and diffusion from
 88 oxic systems is too slow: *in situ* dark oxygen production.
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90
 91 **Figure 1: Processes involved in the production, recycling, and consumption of O₂ in modern environments.**
 92 Reactions responsible for net O₂ production (reactions 1-4) are shown above, and those that recycle or consume O₂
 93 (reaction 5 -9) below the dotted line. Abiotic reactions are shown to the left and biotic reactions to the right of the
 94 dashed line. Note: intermediate reactions and electrons are not shown. This overview highlights the reactions reviewed
 95 here and is not exhaustive, e.g., most abiotic and biotic O₂ consuming redox reactions are not shown.
 96

97 **Biochemistry and physiology of microbial light-independent oxygen production**

98 Of the enzymes involved in microbial DOP, chlorite dismutase (CLD) is the best understood. CLD
 99 is a relatively small heme-dependent enzyme (~120 Da) that consists of two (Celis *et al.* 2015) or
 100 four identical subunits (van Ginkel *et al.* 1996; Mehboob *et al.* 2009). It is highly specific for the

101 dismutation of chlorite to chloride and O₂ with no other side products (Lee *et al.* 2008). The
102 organisms capable of chlorite dismutation are specialized on the reductive dissimilation of
103 (per)chlorate into chloride, with chlorite being a strongly oxidative and toxic intermediate (Xu and
104 Logan 2003; Coates and Achenbach 2004). Although facultative anaerobes, some of these
105 organisms can use the generated O₂ for aerobic degradation of organics (Carlström *et al.* 2015).
106 The details concerning the biochemical properties of CLD and the physiology of (per)chlorate
107 reducers are thoroughly discussed and reviewed elsewhere (Coates and Achenbach 2004; Mlynek
108 *et al.* 2011; Hofbauer *et al.* 2014; Schaffner *et al.* 2015, 2017) and are not the focus of this review.

109 Less is known about the inner workings of the enzymes involved in nitric oxide dismutation
110 because the putative nitric oxide dismutase (NOD) has not been biochemically or structurally
111 characterized. A putative NOD was first postulated as a key enzyme in the nitrite-driven anaerobic
112 oxidation of methane performed by *Candidatus Methylopirabilis oxyfera* (Ettwig *et al.* 2010).
113 While living in anoxic ecosystems, these organisms generate oxygen internally from nitrite—a
114 process which involves NOD—then use generated O₂ to oxidize methane via an aerobic metabolic
115 pathway (Wu *et al.* 2011). It seems clear that the putative NOD evolved from the closely related
116 quinol-dependent nitric oxide reductase (qNOR), because both enzymes belong to the heme-
117 copper oxidoreductase superfamily (Ettwig *et al.* 2012; Murali, Hemp and Gennis 2022). NOD
118 seems to have lost a quinol binding site and thus cannot take up external electrons (Ettwig *et al.*
119 2012), indicating its adaptation for a purpose different from its ancestral scaffold.

120 In pure cultures, O₂ generation coupled to N₂ or N₂O production from nitrite is indicative
121 of NO dismutation. As O₂ production and consumption may be tightly coupled, inhibitors of the
122 O₂-consuming processes (e.g., respiration and ammonia or methane oxidation) may be required to
123 observe oxygen accumulation (Ettwig *et al.* 2010; Kraft *et al.* 2022). In most cases, the ability of
124 microorganisms—including in the ammonium-oxidizing archaeon *Nitrosopumilus maritimus*
125 (Kraft *et al.* 2022) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Lichtenberg *et al.* 2021)—to produce O₂ from
126 nitrite or nitric oxide was shown via ¹⁵N-isotope labelling combined with low-concentration O₂
127 optode measurements. However, neither the genome of *N. maritimus* nor of *P. aeruginosa* encodes
128 a *nod* gene, and the enzyme that is responsible for catalyzing NO dismutation in these organisms
129 remains to be discovered. The presence of two distinct pathways to dismutate NO, which involve
130 different key enzymes, indicates that the capability of NO-dismutation evolved independently at
131 least twice.

132 Several key differences exist in the physiologies of the NO dismutation pathways of *Ca.*
133 *M. oxyfera*, *N. maritimus*, and *P. aeruginosa*. Firstly, *Ca. M. oxyfera* consumes all O₂ that it
134 produces directly for its own metabolism, whereas O₂ accumulates up to concentrations of several
135 hundred nanomole per liter in *N. maritimus* cultures (Kraft *et al.* 2022). Secondly, although both
136 pathways reduce nitrite to NO that is then dismutated, *Ca. M. oxyfera* dismutates NO to O₂ and N₂
137 directly, whereas *N. maritimus* dismutates NO to O₂ and N₂O that is subsequently reduced to N₂
138 (**Fig. 2**). Thirdly, *P. aeruginosa* cultures produce a short-lived O₂ peak that occurs immediately
139 after O₂ is depleted through respiration. Although this peak transiently exceeds O₂ concentrations

140 accumulated by *N. maritimus*, the products, stoichiometry, and responsible enzyme remain to be
141 resolved.

142 In summary, while O₂ is produced in all NO dismutation pathways, the byproducts differ.
143 One implication is that ammonia-oxidizing archaea produce half the amount of O₂ per nitrite
144 consumed as compared to *Ca. M. oxyfera*. In environments in which nitrite is limiting and NO-
145 dismutating microbes compete with other nitrite consuming microbes such as denitrifiers, this
146 could constitute a substantial disadvantage. Finally, recent research indicates that the number of
147 potential dismutation substrates discovered to date may not be exhausted. For example, it was
148 suggested that novel *Methylomirabilota* methanotrophs potentially couple methane oxidation to
149 iodate reduction via the production of O₂ from hypiodous acid (Zhu *et al.* 2022). Future work is
150 therefore needed to explore additional possible dismutating metabolisms.

151

1) Chlorite dismutation

2) Nitric oxide dismutation

a) example: *Candidatus Methylomirabilis oxyfera*

b) example: *Nitrosopumilus maritimus*

152

153

154 **Figure 2: Overview of the different microbial DOP metabolisms.** Reported Gibbs free energies (ΔG) only refer to
155 the O₂ generating step of each process. 1) Chlorite dismutation (Mehboob *et al.* 2009). 2a) NO dismutation to N₂ and
156 O₂ (Ettwig *et al.* 2010), 2b) NO dismutation to N₂O and O₂ (Kraft *et al.* 2022). Pcr: perchlorate reductase, Clr: chlorate
157 reductase, Cld: chlorite dismutase, NirS: Fe-nitrite reductase, Nod: NO-dismutase, NirK: Cu-nitrite reductase, unk:
158 unknown.

159

160 Diversity and phylogeny of *nod* genes and of organisms potentially mediating DOP

161 Organisms that have the metabolic capabilities to dismutate chlorite or nitric oxide are found
162 across the tree of life. For example, it has long been known that CLD is widespread in
163 *Pseudomonas sp.* (Mehboob *et al.* 2009), *Nitrospira sp.* (Maixner *et al.* 2008), *Nitrobacter sp.*
164 (*Mlynek et al.* 2011), *Klebsiella sp.* (Celis *et al.* 2015), as well as in all (per)chlorate respiring
165 organisms such as *Dechloromonas sp.*, *Dechlorosoma sp.* (Coates *et al.* 1999; Achenbach *et al.*
166 2001). Furthermore, a recent publication showed the presence of *cld* genes in organisms affiliated
167 with >60 genera within 13 phyla, mostly among *Proteobacteria* (Barnum and Coates 2023).

168 The list of organisms that are known to contain the *nod* gene is nearly as extensive as that
169 for *cld* and has rapidly expanded in recent years. In particular, there are at least five *Candidatus*

170 species within the *Methylomirabilota* that contain *nod* genes: *Ca. Methylomirabilis oxyfera*, *Ca.*
171 *M. lanthaniphila*, *Ca. M. sinica*, *Ca. M. limnetica*, and *Ca. M. iodofontis* (Ettwig *et al.* 2010; He
172 *et al.* 2016; Graf *et al.* 2018; Versantvoort *et al.* 2018; Zhu *et al.* 2022). In addition to
173 *Methylomirabilota*, *nod* genes were detected in *Sediminibacterium sp.*, *Algoriphagus sp.*, and
174 *Muricauda sp.*—all within the phylum *Bacteroidota* (Ettwig *et al.* 2012; Murali, Hemp and Gennis
175 2022; Ruff *et al.* 2023)—as well as in *Planctomycetota* and *Proteobacteria* (Hanke *et al.* 2016;
176 Murali, Hemp and Gennis 2022; Elbon, Stewart and Glass 2024; Lv *et al.* 2024). The alkane-
177 oxidizing *Gammaproteobacteria* HdN1 contain a putative *nod* and may use oxygen for the
178 activation of alkanes, although the process and activity of this NOD remain unclear (Zedelius *et*
179 *al.* 2011). An even larger diversity of putative *nod* genes has been found through PCR-based
180 studies and environmental surveys (Zhu *et al.* 2017, 2019, 2020; Zhang *et al.* 2018; Hu *et al.* 2019).
181 Furthermore, *nod*-like genes have been reported in viral genomes in oceanic oxygen-deficient
182 zones (Gazitúa *et al.* 2021) as well as in foraminifera colonizing oxygen-depleted sediments
183 (Gomaa *et al.* 2021).

184 To expand upon the diversity of microorganisms that contain *nod* genes, we identified all
185 *nod* sequences within the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) (Parks *et al.* 2022). In doing so,
186 we show that at least 16 phyla and 162 genera contain *nod* genes (**Supplementary Table 1**).
187 Remarkably, more than half of the identified *nod* genes are affiliated with lineages within the
188 phylum *Bacteroidota*. Our phylogenetic analysis of NOD sequences shows that this protein
189 family—belonging to the larger heme-copper oxidoreductase superfamily—diverges into 4
190 subclades, two of which almost exclusively comprise sequences affiliating with *Bacteroidota* (**Fig.**
191 **3**). These clades appear to be robust, sharing no more than 40-50 % sequence similarity between
192 the groups.

193 We also supplemented environmental surveys from PCR-based studies (**Fig. 4A**;
194 **Supplementary Table 2**) by categorizing the environments in which we identified *nod*-containing
195 metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) in our GTDB analysis (**Fig. 4B**; **Supplementary Table**
196 **2**). Our analysis shows that *nod* genes were found in metagenomes from both natural environments
197 such as lakes, hydrothermal vents, and methane seeps, as well as in man-made environments such
198 as waste-water treatment plants and bioreactors. This supports earlier marker gene-based studies
199 in which *nod* genes were found in lake sediment, wetlands, aquifers, soils, oil reservoirs and
200 wastewater treatment plants (Zhu *et al.* 2017, 2020; Zhang *et al.* 2018; Hu *et al.* 2019).
201 Interestingly, the *nod* genes occurred in such artificial environments at higher abundances than in
202 natural environments, and there existed no trend between the phylogenetic affiliation of *nod* genes
203 and their environmental distribution. This most likely reflects the diverse lifestyles of
204 microorganisms capable of *nod*-mediated DOP. For example, microbes affiliating with
205 *Bacteroidota* thrive in many anoxic environments ranging from organic acid rich marine sediments
206 to bioreactors. Their presence in these environments is largely consistent with biogeochemical
207 evidence for microbial DOP in these environments.

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211 **Figure 3: Phylogenetic diversity and taxonomic distribution of nitric oxide dismutases (NOD).** NOD sequences
 212 were retrieved from release 214 of the Genome Taxonomy Database (Parks *et al.* 2022) using a Hidden Markov Model
 213 (HMM) built with curated NOD sequences (Murali, Hemp and Gennis 2022). These sequences were aligned using
 214 MUSCLE (Edgar 2004) and a phylogenetic tree was inferred using IQ-TREE (Minh *et al.* 2020) with qNOR sequences
 215 as outgroup. A substitution model was identified with IQ-TREE's ModelFinder and the tree was validated with a 1000
 216 ultrafast bootstraps. The tree was visualized using iTOL, and the label background of each leaf on the tree was colored
 217 according to the phylum of the bacteria or archaea that contained the *nod* (**Supplementary Table 1**). The phylum
 218 level classification was made according to GTDB taxonomy. The tree appeared to diverge into four clades, each of
 219 which is color-coded here. The protein accession ID of each sequence in the tree according to GTDB is available in
 220 **Supplementary Table 1**.

221

222 Occurrence of O₂-dependent enzymes, metabolisms, and microbes in anoxic environments

223 In addition to the widespread occurrence of microorganisms that have the metabolic capabilities
 224 to produce O₂ in the absence of light, there are many records of the presence of O₂-consuming,
 225 strictly aerobic organisms and metabolic pathways in supposedly anoxic environments. Despite
 226 not being detectable using traditional methods, O₂ is likely produced and consumed in these
 227 environments as indicated, for example, by the occurrence and expression of O₂-dependent
 228 oxygenases. Below we outline evidence for active O₂ cycling in a non-exhaustive list of select
 229 environments.

230

231 *Marine environments*

232 In the marine environment, gene transcripts of oxygenases and the presence of strict aerobes were
233 reported from oxygen-deficient water bodies. In particular, O₂-dependent monooxygenases
234 (Hayashi *et al.* 2007; Tavormina *et al.* 2013; Padilla *et al.* 2017) and aerobic respiration were found
235 in the oxygen-deficient waters off the coast of Namibia, Mexico, and Peru (Tiano *et al.* 2014;
236 Kalvelage *et al.* 2015). The presence of O₂ in oxygen minimum zones (OMZs) is often attributed
237 to laterally or vertically advected “whiffs”, which is certainly a possible explanation for the
238 prevalence of aerobic microbes. However, the presence of oxygenic phototrophs (Garcia-Robledo
239 *et al.* 2017) and of microbes expressing *nod* genes (Padilla *et al.* 2016; Elbon, Stewart and Glass
240 2024) in OMZs also indicates the potential for in situ production—with or without light—as an O₂
241 source. Despite this possible importance, such production is difficult to detect directly because
242 trace levels of produced O₂ in OMZs would not be expected to accumulate to detectable levels but,
243 would likely be consumed immediately (Canfield and Kraft 2022).

244 Evidence for the activity of aerobes was also found several meters below the seafloor of
245 the permanently anoxic Arabian Sea OMZ (Bhattacharya *et al.* 2020). These sediments contained
246 obligate aerobes, that upon isolation only grew with oxygen. Also *Nitrosopumilus sp.* and *nod*
247 genes were present and oxidase genes were transcribed (Sarkar *et al.* 2024). In marine seeps and
248 mud volcanoes, aerobic methanotrophs are abundant in methane-rich sediments well below the
249 measurable oxygen penetration depth (Lösekann *et al.* 2007; Ruff *et al.* 2013, 2015, 2019). It was
250 speculated that these sediments may be actively oxygenated, e.g. by bioturbation due to seep-
251 associated fauna. *Nitrosopumilaceae* as well as *Methylomirabilota* are also very widespread and
252 often abundant in deep subseafloor sediments indicating a genetic potential for dark oxygen
253 production in environments that have been disconnected from surface processes on geologic time
254 scales (Ruff *et al.* 2024).

255 *Lake and wetland environments*

256 Aerobic methanotrophs have been detected in anoxic sediments of thermokarst Lake Vault, Alaska
257 (Martinez-Cruz *et al.* 2017), as well as in sediments (up to 70 cm) at an active methane seep in
258 Lake Qalluuraq, Alaska (He *et al.* 2022). Anoxic mesocosms using sediments from both sites
259 contained aerobic gammaproteobacterial methanotrophs that dominated methane assimilation, as
260 shown by DNA-based stable isotope probing (Martinez-Cruz *et al.* 2017; He *et al.* 2022). In the
261 seep site, the authors speculate that methanotrophy was coupled to iron reduction, yet it is unlikely
262 that at least the first step of methane activation using the *pmoA* gene would occur without O₂.
263 Evidence of aerobic methanotrophy has also been detected in the suboxic/upper anoxic zones of
264 Lake Untersee, Antarctica (Brady, Andersen and Slater 2023). Similar observations were made in
265 Lake Zug, Switzerland, with methanotrophs belonging to *Gammaproteobacteria* and
266 *Alphaproteobacteria*. The aerobic alpha- and gammaproteobacterial methanotrophs were found to
267 be more abundant in anoxic waters than in the oxycline and oxic waters (Oswald *et al.* 2016). The
268 same authors reported a bloom of denitrifying methanotrophs affiliating with *Methylomirabilota*
269 in the anoxic layer (Graf *et al.* 2018).

270 The purple sulfur bacteria *Chromatium okenii* thriving in Lake Cadagno, Switzerland, has
271 been found to aerobically oxidize sulfide in dark and apparently anoxic waters. Authors have
272 hypothesized that in this case, O₂ could come from transport and active convection process
273 occurring in the lake, allowing microbial population at the oxic/anoxic interface to be active (Berg
274 *et al.* 2019). In addition to convection of O₂, the hypothesis of local microbial DOP could be
275 contemplated. The anoxic water column of Lake Lugano, Switzerland, comprised *pmoA* genes in
276 the anoxic portion of the water column, but not in the oxic portion. Most of the detected bacterial
277 populations affiliated with *Methylobacter* sp. and showed maximum activity at the suboxic-anoxic
278 interface and in the deeper anoxic layer (Blees *et al.* 2014). In the boreal lake Alinen-Mustajärvi,
279 Finland, aerobic methanotrophic *Methylobacter* and newly described Ca. *Methyloumidiphilus*
280 *alinesnsis* were active and transcripts of *pmoA* were present in the anoxic hypolimnion and in dark
281 and anaerobic incubations (Rissanen *et al.* 2018). The addition of nitrate to the incubations
282 stimulated methane oxidation, and the authors speculate that trace amounts of O₂ could have
283 diffused through or out of the septa allowing the micro-aerobic methane activation and subsequent
284 coupling to denitrification (Rissanen *et al.* 2018).

285 Similar to lakes, *Methylobacter* sequences have been found to be active in an Arctic
286 wetland, with the highest activity detected in the anoxic zone and the transition zone (Graef *et al.*
287 2011). Further, *Methylobacter* and *Methylococcus* sequences were detected in the Zoige wetland,
288 China, both in oxic and anoxic zones. While the abundance of aerobic methanotrophs was highest
289 in the oxic zone, their diversity was highest in the anoxic zone, which indicates diverse aerobic
290 niches that can support distinct populations of aerobes (Yun *et al.* 2010). Anaerobic continuous
291 cultures inoculated with wetland sediments and fed with methane and nitrous oxide were
292 dominated by aerobic methanotrophic *Methylocaldum* after 500 days; stable isotope analyses and
293 an increase of methane monooxygenase suggested that aerobic methane oxidation was driven by
294 nitrous oxide consumption (Cheng *et al.* 2021). The widespread occurrence, activity and
295 persistence of aerobic methanotrophs in anoxic freshwater habitats was suggested to be caused by
296 diverse mechanisms, including direct electron transfer to metal oxides, alternative electron
297 acceptors and the presence of intracellular gas vesicles (Reis *et al.* 2024). Our work adds DOP to
298 the list of possible processes that can explain aerobic niches in anoxic wetland habitats.

299 *Groundwater and subsurface environments*

300 Ammonium-oxidizing archaea (AOA), which require O₂ for the activation of ammonium to
301 hydroxylamine, have been found together with *Methylomirabilota* in dysoxic aquifers (Mosley *et*
302 *al.* 2022). These authors speculated that O₂ is provided to AOA by *Methylomirabilota* via
303 microbial cooperation; such a dark-O₂ “leakage” into the surrounding environment has indeed
304 been observed in a laboratory setup (Kraft *et al.* 2022). However, as described in detail above, it
305 was the AOA *N. maritimus* that has been shown to produce and leak O₂ in dark and anoxic
306 conditions (Kraft *et al.* 2022), thus obviating the need to invoke *Methylomirabilota* as an O₂ source.
307 Microbial O₂ leakage from chlorite or nitric oxide dismutation could also explain the presence of
308 oxygen and the observed co-existence of strictly aerobic methanotrophic *Methylobacter* with *nod*
309 and *cld* gene-containing organisms in old groundwaters (Ruff *et al.* 2023). A laboratory experiment

310 using sand-packed microcosms and groundwater as inoculum showed that methane oxidation in
311 these *Methylobacter*-dominated microcosms was strictly dependent on oxygen, despite the
312 presence of nitrate, which indicates that oxygen is needed for the activation of methane even if the
313 oxidation of methanol can be coupled to denitrification (Kuloyo *et al.* 2020). Deep aquifer systems
314 can also contain viable aerobic heterotrophs that are indicative of a relatively oxidizing
315 environment (Hicks and Fredrickson 1989).

316 Groundwater environments are often contaminated with hydrocarbons from industrial or
317 military facilities. Interestingly, benzene-contaminated aquifers have been shown to comprise
318 aerobic and denitrifying communities at low- to below-detection-limit O₂ concentrations (Aburto
319 *et al.* 2009). The characterization of benzene-oxidizing and chlorate-reducing enrichment cultures
320 indicated that anaerobic benzene degradation could be bypassed by DOP from chlorate-reducing
321 communities (Weelink *et al.* 2007). In another study, O₂ production was measured during benzene-
322 degradation under nitrate-reducing conditions (Atashgahi *et al.* 2018). For the toluene-degrading
323 microbe *Georgfuchsia toluolica* it was shown that traces of O₂ being introduced during sampling
324 are enough to supply O₂ for the enzymatic steps of aerobic toluene degradation which require it,
325 while the main electron flux and energy generation occurred simultaneously via nitrate reduction
326 (Atashgahi *et al.* 2021). This shows that very small amounts of O₂, e.g. supplied by DOP, can
327 suffice for the initial activation of hydrocarbons, and establish aerobic niches in anoxic
328 environments.

329 Strictly aerobic methanotrophs have also been found in lignite and coal formations (Mills
330 *et al.* 2010; Stepniewska, Pytlak and Kuźniar 2013, 2014; Pytlak *et al.* 2014). Similarly, cores from
331 oil sands and coal beds in Alberta have been shown to contain unexpectedly high proportions of
332 aerobic hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria as well as metagenomes with high proportions of genes
333 for enzymes involved in aerobic hydrocarbon metabolism (An *et al.* 2013). Even deep crystalline
334 bedrock seems to comprise strictly aerobic methanotrophs, which need O₂ for the activation of
335 methane to methanol (Kalyuzhnaya *et al.* 1999; Hirayama *et al.* 2011; Kietäväinen and Purkamo
336 2015; Rajala *et al.* 2015). Water samples from rock fractures of the Deep Mine Microbial
337 Observatory comprised methane monooxygenases and other enzymes for oxygen respiration
338 (Momper, Casar and Osburn 2023). Ancient fluids of Canadian shield bedrock contained viable
339 heterotrophic aerobes that apparently belonged to an indigenous community (Song *et al.* 2024).
340 Radiolysis of water is a source of O₂ in certain subsurface systems, and could explain, for example,
341 the presence of strict aerobes in sediment and rock layers near a uranium mine (Mills *et al.* 2010).
342 However, widespread occurrence and substantial concentrations of dissolved O₂ in subsurface
343 ecosystems merit a closer investigation of other possible processes.

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Figure 4 Environmental distribution of *nod* genes. (A) Map of *nod* gene presence and abundance reported in the literature (Supplementary Table 2). (B) Phylogenetic tree showing NOD sequences colored by the environments in which they were identified as described in the metadata accompanying the BioSample of each MAG from which the *nod* gene was recovered (Supplementary Table 2). The 4 clades identified in the *nod* phylogenetic tree in Fig. 3 were colored in the same shades to correlate the distribution of NOD clades in different environments. BTEX: Benzene, toluene, and xylenes, WWTP: Wastewater treatment plant

355 **Detecting and quantifying dark oxygen production**

356 Dissolved oxygen has been detected in many subsurface ecosystems, including deep oxygenated
357 groundwater (Winograd and Robertson 1982; Ronen *et al.* 1987) and fluids within ancient bedrock
358 (Nisson *et al.* 2023). Despite the widespread detection and occurrence of O₂ and putative O₂-
359 producing enzymes and metabolisms in supposedly anoxic environments, confidently quantifying
360 the amount of O₂ produced in situ remains challenging, particularly using traditional
361 microbiological tools. The most promising method to date to distinguish atmospherically derived
362 from in situ produced dissolved oxygen—and to quantify their relative proportions—remains
363 stable oxygen isotope analysis. The utility of this approach largely relies on the so-called “Dole
364 effect” (Dole, 1936), in which isotope fractionation during oxic respiration leads to atmospheric
365 O₂ being enriched in ¹⁸O by several tens of permil relative to water (i.e., δ¹⁸O = 24 ‰ for
366 atmospheric O₂; δ¹⁸O ranging from ~ -25 to 0 ‰ for typical meteoric waters and seawater (Sharp,
367 Wostbrock and Pack 2018; Wostbrock, Cano and Sharp 2020)¹. In contrast to respiration,
368 photosynthesis, and likely dark oxygen production, generate O₂ with an isotopic composition
369 lighter than bulk atmosphere derived O₂. The isotopic composition of photosynthesis-derived O₂
370 resembles that of the parent water from which it formed (Helman *et al.* 2005). The isotopic
371 composition of DOP-derived O₂ is currently unknown because DOP fractionation factors remain
372 unconstrained. The detection of dissolved oxygen that is depleted in ¹⁸O relative to atmospheric O₂
373 therefore likely implies in situ production, the amount of which is quantitatively related to the
374 difference in δ¹⁸O value between atmospheric O₂ and measured dissolved oxygen.

375 Following these principles, several studies have analyzed δ¹⁸O values of dissolved oxygen
376 in groundwaters to constrain O₂ cycling dynamics (Aggarwal and Dillon 1998; Révész *et al.* 1999;
377 Wassenaar and Hendry 2007; Smith *et al.* 2011; Parker *et al.* 2012, 2014; Ruff *et al.* 2023), which
378 we compiled here (**Fig. 5A**). Authors typically assume that groundwater initially contains dissolved
379 O₂ in equilibrium with the atmosphere. If this dissolved O₂ subsequently undergoes closed-system
380 consumption either by microbial respiration or by abiotic processes (e.g., Fe(II) or H₂S oxidation;
381 Oba and Poulson 2009a, 2009b), then residual dissolved oxygen δ¹⁸O values will become
382 progressively higher due to isotopic fractionation (so-called “Rayleigh fractionation”). Such
383 mechanisms successfully explain ≈35 % of all groundwater observations compiled here (values
384 that plot between the green and blue/orange shaded regions in **Fig. 5A**).

385 However, many studies also observe ¹⁸O-depleted dissolved oxygen in groundwater. This
386 cannot be explained by consumption mechanisms alone, all of which are expected to lead to ¹⁸O
387 enrichment (Mader *et al.* 2017). Rather, these authors have mostly invoked downward diffusion of
388 atmospheric O₂ through the vadose zone to explain ¹⁸O-depleted values in shallow aquifers (Smith

¹The major stable-oxygen isotope composition of any oxygen-bearing material is written as

$$\delta^{18}\text{O} = \left(\frac{{}^{18}\text{R}_{\text{sample}}}{{}^{18}\text{R}_{\text{VSMOW}}} - 1 \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where ¹⁸R is the ¹⁸O/¹⁶O ratio and VSMOW is the Vienna Standard Mean Ocean Water international standard. Results are often reported in units of “permil” (‰) by multiplying Eq. 1 by 1000.

389 et al. 2011; Parker et al. 2012, 2014). Diffusion is known to induce isotopic fractionation due to
 390 differences in isotopologue-specific diffusion coefficients; this process can thus lead to ^{18}O -
 391 depleted dissolved oxygen despite being derived from atmospheric O_2 , but only in low
 392 concentrations (Knox, Quay and Wilbur 1992; Li et al. 2019; Cao 2022). As diffusion-derived
 393 dissolved oxygen concentrations increase, isotopic compositions approach their equilibrium value
 394 of $\delta^{18}\text{O} \approx 24 \text{‰}$ (green shaded regions in Figure 5). By considering diffusion in addition to
 395 consumption, the percentage of groundwater observations compiled here that can be explained by
 396 traditional mechanisms increases to $\approx 53 \%$. This analysis thus suggests nearly half of all
 397 groundwater dissolved oxygen $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values compiled here can only be explained by invoking an
 398 additional source of ^{18}O -depleted O_2 , for example by in situ dark oxygen production. Such
 399 processes—regardless of specific biotic vs. abiotic mechanism—will drive groundwater dissolved
 400 oxygen to higher concentrations and lower $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values (red arrows in Fig. 5).
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 403 **Figure 5: Groundwater dissolved oxygen isotope plots** showing (A) $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ as a function of dissolved oxygen
 404 concentration [DO] and (B) $\Delta^{17}\text{O}$ as a function of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (so-called “triple-oxygen isotope plot”). Modern-day
 405 atmospheric O_2 isotopic composition (Wostbrock, Cano and Sharp 2020) is shown in panel B as an open white circle.
 406 Dissolved O_2 is assumed to begin in equilibrium with the atmosphere at standard temperature and pressure in fluids
 407 between 5 and 15°C with salinity between 0 and 10 psu (thick black line in panel A; black circle in panel B; using
 408 published concentrations (Garcia and Gordon 1992) and fractionation factors (Li *et al.* 2019)). Groundwater dissolved
 409 O_2 can then decrease in concentration and become isotopically fractionated via consumption by microbial respiration
 410 (blue shaded region) or abiotic processes (e.g., Fe(II) or H_2S oxidation; orange shaded region). Both consumption
 411 processes are assumed to follow closed-system Rayleigh fractionation with a range of fractionation factors for
 412 respiration (Stolper, Fischer and Bender 2018; Ash, Hu and Yeung 2020; Sutherland *et al.* 2022) and abiotic
 413 consumption (Oba and Poulson 2009b, 2009a). To estimate triple-oxygen isotope fractionation factors for abiotic
 414 O_2 consumption, orange shaded region in panel B includes the full range of fractionation factors observed for H_2O_2
 415 consumption (Sutherland, Hemingway and Johnston 2022), assuming abiotic O_2 consumption occurs via a reactive-

416 oxygen species intermediate. Balancing consumption, groundwater dissolved O₂ concentrations can increase either by
 417 inward diffusion from overlying vadose zone or by microbial (e.g., nitric oxide or chlorite dismutation) or abiotic (e.g.,
 418 water radiolysis) in situ production. Following the diffusion model of Smith et al. (2011) with isotope fractionation
 419 factors from Knox et al. (1992) and Li et al. (2019), as interpreted by Cao (2022), inward diffusing O₂ is initially ¹⁸O-
 420 depleted and ¹⁷O-enriched at low DO concentrations; it approaches equilibrium values as concentrations increase
 421 (green shaded regions). Mixing between inward-diffusing O₂ and water that has undergone dissolved O₂ consumption
 422 will result in isotope values that plot between the green and blue/orange shaded regions. In contrast, mixing with in
 423 situ produced O₂ shifts isotopic compositions toward an end member resembling source water (modified by
 424 fractionation during the O₂ production process). For example, the red arrow indicates in situ production starting from
 425 an arbitrary initial point within the respiration array (red diamond) assuming that in situ O₂ forms from groundwater
 426 with δ¹⁸O = -17.5 ‰ and Δ¹⁷O = 84 ppm, i.e., the average of all measured values compiled here, assuming they fall
 427 on the meteoric water line as previously reported (Sharp, Wostbrock and Pack 2018) and assuming that O₂/H₂O
 428 fractionation is described by the temperature-dependent equilibrium fractionation factor (Hemingway *et al.* 2022).
 429 Regardless of the exact fractionation factors, in situ production is the only process within this framework that can
 430 explain high concentrations of ¹⁸O-depleted dissolved O₂ (i.e., to the lower-right of the diffusion array). Gray circles
 431 in panel A represent 338 measured values from globally distributed groundwaters (Aggarwal and Dillon 1998; Révész
 432 *et al.* 1999; Wassenaar and Hendry 2007; Smith *et al.* 2011; Parker *et al.* 2012, 2014; Ruff *et al.* 2023). Nearly half of
 433 all measurements are best explained by in situ production of isotopically light oxygen (**Supplementary Table 3**).
 434

435 In addition to canonical ¹⁸O measurements, recent analytical advancements have led to
 436 increased use of so called “triple-oxygen isotopes” (written as Δ¹⁷O)² to track oxygen cycling.
 437 Of relevance here is the fact that atmospheric O₂ is anomalously depleted in ¹⁷O due to mass-
 438 independent isotope exchange processes in the stratosphere (Hemingway and Claire). This leads
 439 to atmospheric O₂ with a Δ¹⁷O value of ≈ -500 ppm. In contrast, seawater and all meteoric fluids
 440 fall along a mass-dependent meteoric water line, with Δ¹⁷O ≥ 0 ppm (Sharp, Wostbrock and Pack
 441 2018). Like in δ¹⁸O vs. dissolved oxygen concentration space, several processes of interest here
 442 will lead to unique fractionation trajectories in a triple-oxygen isotope plot (**Fig. 5B**). Importantly,
 443 only by combining all three measurements—concentration, δ¹⁸O, and Δ¹⁷O—can the source and
 444 cycling of dissolved oxygen be uniquely constrained. For example, partial closed-system
 445 respiration followed by dark oxygen production could be falsely interpreted as reflecting diffusion
 446 in a concentration vs. δ¹⁸O plot (intersection of red arrow and green shaded region in **Fig. 5A**), but
 447 these processes can be uniquely separated when including Δ¹⁷O (no intersection of red arrow and
 448 green shaded region in **Fig. 5B**).
 449

450 **Astrobiological relevance of DOP**

²The triple-oxygen isotope composition of any oxygen-bearing material is typically written as

$$\Delta^{17}\text{O} = \ln \left(\frac{{}^{17}\text{R}_{\text{sample}}}{{}^{17}\text{R}_{\text{VSMOW}}} \right) - \theta_{\text{RL}} \times \ln \left(\frac{{}^{18}\text{R}_{\text{sample}}}{{}^{18}\text{R}_{\text{VSMOW}}} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where ¹⁷R is the ¹⁷O/¹⁶O ratio and θ_{RL} is a reference line slope. Here, we let θ_{RL} = 0.5305 (Bao, Cao and Hayles 2016). Results are often reported in units of “parts per million” (ppm) by multiplying Eq. 2 by 10⁶.

451 Atmospheric production of (per)chlorate occurs in earth's stratosphere from oxidation of Cl^- , ClO^-
452 x or ClO_x through ozone or light (Sturchio *et al.* 2009; Jackson *et al.* 2010), whereas nitrate is
453 formed through oxidation of nitrogen dioxide gas to nitric acid (Smith *et al.* 2014). Accumulation
454 of these compounds after deposition on the Earth's surface correlates with aridity, thus explaining
455 the elevated levels of (per)chlorate in dry conditions such as those of the Atacama Desert (Catling
456 *et al.* 2010). Evidence exists that both nitrate and (per)chlorate also occur on the lunar surface, on
457 Mars, and within Martian meteorites (Kounaves *et al.* 2014; Stern *et al.* 2015; Martin *et al.* 2020),
458 with detected nitrate levels in Martian sediments (up to 1,000 ppm; (Stern *et al.* 2015) reaching
459 those found in the Atacama Desert (Walvoord *et al.* 2003). Microbial enrichment cultures from
460 this nitrate-rich arid environment have shown microbial growth possibility (Shen *et al.* 2019), and
461 $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{ClO}_4^-$ reducing microbial populations were identified from desert soil samples that serve as
462 sites analogous to the Martian environment (Cortés *et al.* 2024). Due to highly conserved ratio of
463 $\text{NO}_3^-/\text{ClO}_4^-$ in non-biologically active areas on Earth, it may be possible to use alterations of this
464 ratio as a biomarker of past biological activity on Mars (Jackson *et al.* 2015).

465 Subsurface nitrates on Mars could potentially provide a source of available nitrogen and
466 O_2 to support past or present life, which is most likely found in the planet's subsurface ecosystems
467 (Michalski *et al.* 2018). Aerobic niches caused by DOP could in theory be present also in dark
468 environments on ocean worlds, as biologically available nitrogen was detected in Enceladus'
469 plume. Furthermore, Enceladus' global ocean is suspected to harbor hydrothermal activity (Hsu *et*
470 *al.* 2015; Waite *et al.* 2017). On Earth, hydrothermal systems present available forms of nitrogen
471 and are colonized by a variety of microorganisms involved in the nitrogen cycle (Zeng, Alain and
472 Shao 2021). Hydrothermal systems additionally drive abiotic O_2 generation via the surface-bound
473 radical mechanism (Stone *et al.* 2022). DOP—whether abiotic or biotic—could therefore be a
474 source of O_2 in hydrothermally active, nitrate-rich ocean worlds even if light is not available.
475

476
 477 **Figure 6: Overview of apparently anoxic ecosystems that have been reported to contain traces of oxygen,**
 478 **comprise aerobic microorganisms, or O₂-producing or -consuming metabolic genes.** Traces of oxygen were found
 479 in old groundwaters (e.g., Winograd and Robertson 1982, Ruff *et al.* 2023) and fracture fluids (e.g., Nisson *et al.*
 480 2023), while aerobic microorganisms and oxygen-dependent enzymes were reported from a variety of anoxic systems,
 481 such as bedrock, groundwater, marine and freshwater sediments and hydrocarbon reservoirs. These microbes were
 482 associated with oxidation of methane, other hydrocarbons, and ammonia (e.g., Hayashi *et al.* 2007; Tavormina *et al.*
 483 2013; Padilla *et al.* 2017, Tiano *et al.* 2014; Kalvelage *et al.* 2015, Martinez-Cruz *et al.* 2017, He *et al.* 2022, Lösekann
 484 *et al.* 2007; Ruff *et al.* 2013, 2019, Bhattacharya *et al.* 2020, Mosley *et al.* 2022, Aburto *et al.* 2009, Mills *et al.* 2010;
 485 Stępniewska, Pytlak and Kuźniar 2013, 2014; Pytlak *et al.* 2014). Expression of *nod* and *cld* genes was detected in
 486 oxygen-deficient waters, sediments, groundwater and wastewater treatment plants (e.g., Padilla *et al.* 2016; Elbon,
 487 Stewart and Glass 2024, Sarkar *et al.* 2024, Ruff *et al.* 2024, Ruff *et al.* 2023, Bhattacharjee *et al.* 2016, Cheng *et al.*
 488 2021).

489
 490 **Concluding remarks and outlook**

491 Following a quote from the 1982 paper “Deep Oxygenated Groundwater: Anomaly or Common
 492 Occurrence?” (Winograd and Robertson 1982) in which the authors write: “We hope that this
 493 report will stimulate a systematic appraisal of DO [dissolved oxygen] in future geochemical studies
 494 of shallow and deep ground water” we would like to conclude this review on similar hopes.
 495 Oxygen anomalies have been reported from numerous environments, aerobic organisms are
 496 widespread in anoxic ecosystems, and the metabolic capabilities to produce oxygen via
 497 dismutation of chlorite or nitric oxide are nearly ubiquitous. In contrast to the early 1980’s, we

498 now have advanced molecular tools to detect putative *nod* genes, e.g., through specific
499 oligonucleotide primers for gene amplification (Bhattacharjee *et al.* 2016; Zhu *et al.* 2017; Hu *et*
500 *al.* 2019), and achieve high-quality whole genome sequencing data even from low-biomass
501 environments. The widespread availability and utilization of better sequence-similarity tools that
502 include curated Hidden Markov Models to detect target proteins will improve the characterization
503 of genes and pathways involved in DOP and allow us to understand their global diversity,
504 abundance, and evolution. Indeed, our analysis of published sequencing data demonstrates the
505 unexpected and striking occurrence of *nod* genes in the phylum *Bacteroidota* and suggests a role
506 of *Bacteroidota* in NOD-associated DOP. Putting together the environmental co-occurrence
507 between hydrocarbon degradation and DOP, and the genomic potential in many *Bacteroidota* to
508 perform hydrocarbon degradation, we could infer that aerobic hydrocarbon degradation in anoxic
509 environments is one of the major driving forces for the evolutionary selection of DOP well beyond
510 the phylum *Methylomirabilota*. Future studies looking at the co-expression of DOP and
511 hydrocarbon degradation pathways within apparently anoxic environments by gene transcript
512 sequencing, and protein mass spectrometry will provide insight into the relative fluxes of O₂ from
513 DOP into various aerobic pathways.

514 New observational and experimental tools are becoming routinely available to further
515 constrain DOP. For example, the detection limit for bulk dissolved oxygen concentrations has been
516 improved by several orders of magnitude in the last decade (Tiano, Garcia-Robledo and Revsbech
517 2014; Lehner *et al.* 2015; Larsen *et al.* 2016). The measurement of dissolved O₂—including its
518 (triple)-oxygen isotopic composition—should become a standard procedure when measuring and
519 monitoring environmental parameters in subsurface ecosystems, along with nitrate, nitrite,
520 (per)chlorate, and chlorite concentration measurements. If shown to be isotopically unique and
521 utilized in biosynthetic pathways, it may even be possible to track DOP-derived oxygen
522 incorporation into biomolecules such as long-chain alcohols (Johnson and Galy 2022).
523 Furthermore, experiments and incubations using isotopically labelled substrates, for example
524 ¹⁵N¹⁸O, can yield valuable insights into dismutation processes, the involved organisms, and
525 metabolic rates. Finally, heterologous expression of *nod* genes and pathways into a recipient cell
526 such as *E. coli* may shed additional light on the biochemistry of the enzymes of interest.

527 Despite the promise of stable oxygen isotopes as a method to track dark-oxygen
528 production, several key uncertainties remain. In particular, the (triple)-oxygen isotope
529 fractionation factors for many processes of interest are unknown. First, only ¹⁸O fractionation for
530 abiotic O₂ consumption has been determined to date (Oba and Poulson 2009b, 2009a), thus leading
531 to large uncertainty in the triple-oxygen isotope effect of this process. Second, to our knowledge,
532 no fractionation factor measurements currently exist for any in situ dark oxygen production
533 mechanism, neither biological metabolisms nor abiotic processes such as radiolysis. Third, oxygen
534 produced via DOP may not accumulate to high enough levels to assess isotope fractionation due
535 to consumption by nanoaerobic microbes. Future work should aim to directly quantify these
536 fractionation factors using laboratory experiments and culturing studies. Once these fractionation
537 factors have been accurately quantified, then (triple)-oxygen isotope analysis of dissolved oxygen

538 will provide a powerful tool to quantitatively track oxygen cycling, including the effect of dark
539 oxygen production.

540 Overall, in this review we show that dark oxygen production is likely an overlooked
541 process of global relevance not only in subsurface ecosystems, but also in many anoxic ecosystems
542 on Earth's surface. DOP can explain many of the oxygen-related anomalies and enigmatic
543 occurrences of strict aerobes that have been reported for decades and may be crucial for the
544 understanding of the biogeochemistry, ecology, and evolution of diverse environments.

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550

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556

557 **Conflict of interest**

558 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

559

560 **Bibliography**

- 561 Aburto A, Fahy A, Coulon F *et al.* Mixed aerobic and anaerobic microbial communities in
562 benzene-contaminated groundwater. *J Appl Microbiol* 2009;**106**:317–28.
- 563 Achenbach LA, Michaelidou U, Bruce RA *et al.* Dechloromonas agitata gen. nov., sp. nov. and
564 Dechlorosoma suillum gen. nov., sp. nov., two novel environmentally dominant
565 (per)chlorate-reducing bacteria and their phylogenetic position. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol*
566 2001;**51**:527–33.
- 567 Aggarwal PK, Dillon MA. Stable isotope composition of molecular oxygen in soil gas and
568 groundwater: A potentially robust tracer for diffusion and oxygen consumption processes.
569 *Geochim Cosmochim Acta* 1998;**62**:577–84.
- 570 An D, Caffrey SM, Soh J *et al.* Metagenomics of Hydrocarbon Resource Environments Indicates
571 Aerobic Taxa and Genes to be Unexpectedly Common. *Environ Sci Technol*
572 2013;**47**:10708–17.
- 573 Ash JL, Hu H, Yeung LY. What Fractionates Oxygen Isotopes during Respiration? Insights from
574 Multiple Isotopologue Measurements and Theory. *ACS Earth Sp Chem* 2020;**4**:50–66.
- 575 Atashgahi S, Hornung B, van der Waals MJ *et al.* A benzene-degrading nitrate-reducing
576 microbial consortium displays aerobic and anaerobic benzene degradation pathways. *Sci*
577 *Rep* 2018;**8**:4490.
- 578 Atashgahi S, Oosterkamp MJ, Peng P *et al.* Proteogenomic analysis of Georgfuchsia toluolica
579 revealed unexpected concurrent aerobic and anaerobic toluene degradation. *Environ*
580 *Microbiol Rep* 2021;**13**:841–51.

581 Bao H, Cao X, Hayles JA. Triple Oxygen Isotopes: Fundamental Relationships and Applications.
582 *Annu Rev Earth Planet Sci* 2016;**44**:463–92.

583 Barnum TP, Coates JD. Chlorine redox chemistry is widespread in microbiology. *ISME J*
584 2023;**17**:70–83.

585 Berg JS, Ahmerkamp S, Pjevac P *et al.* How low can they go? Aerobic respiration by
586 microorganisms under apparent anoxia. *FEMS Microbiol Rev* 2022;**46**:1–14.

587 Berg JS, Pjevac P, Sommer T *et al.* Dark aerobic sulfide oxidation by anoxygenic phototrophs in
588 anoxic waters. *Environ Microbiol* 2019;**21**:1611–26.

589 Bhattacharjee AS, Motlagh AM, Jetten MSM *et al.* Methane dependent denitrification- from
590 ecosystem to laboratory-scale enrichment for engineering applications. *Water Res*
591 2016;**99**:244–52.

592 Bhattacharya S, Roy C, Mandal S *et al.* Aerobic microbial communities in the sediments of a
593 marine oxygen minimum zone. *FEMS Microbiol Lett* 2020;**367**:1–11.

594 Bles J, Niemann H, Wenk CB *et al.* Micro-aerobic bacterial methane oxidation in the
595 chemocline and anoxic water column of deep south-Alpine Lake Lugano (Switzerland).
596 *Limnol Oceanogr* 2014;**59**:311–24.

597 Brady AL, Andersen DT, Slater GF. Biosignatures of in situ carbon cycling driven by physical
598 isolation and sedimentary methanogenesis within the anoxic basin of perennially ice-
599 covered Lake Untersee, Antarctica. *Biogeochemistry* 2023;**164**:555–75.

600 Le Caër S. Water Radiolysis: Influence of Oxide Surfaces on H₂ Production under Ionizing
601 Radiation. *Water* 2011;**3**:235–53.

602 Canfield DE, Kraft B. The ‘oxygen’ in oxygen minimum zones. *Environ Microbiol*
603 2022;**24**:5332–44.

604 Cao X. Diffusional isotope fractionation of singly and doubly substituted isotopologues of H₂,
605 N₂ and O₂ during air-water gas transfer. *Geochim Cosmochim Acta* 2022;**332**:78–87.

606 Carlström CI, Loutey D, Bauer S *et al.* (Per)Chlorate-Reducing Bacteria Can Utilize Aerobic and
607 Anaerobic Pathways of Aromatic Degradation with (Per)Chlorate as an Electron Acceptor.
608 de Lorenzo V, Lee SY (eds.). *MBio* 2015;**6**:1–12.

609 Catling DC, Claire MW, Zahnle KJ *et al.* Atmospheric origins of perchlorate on Mars and in the
610 Atacama. *J Geophys Res Planets* 2010;**115**:1–15.

611 Catling DC, Glein CR, Zahnle KJ *et al.* Why O₂ Is Required by Complex Life on Habitable
612 Planets and the Concept of Planetary “Oxygenation Time.” *Astrobiology* 2005;**5**:415–38.

613 Celis AI, Geeraerts Z, Ngmenterebo D *et al.* A Dimeric Chlorite Dismutase Exhibits O₂ -
614 Generating Activity and Acts as a Chlorite Antioxidant in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* MGH
615 78578. *Biochemistry* 2015;**54**:434–46.

616 Cheng C, Zhang J, He Q *et al.* Exploring simultaneous nitrous oxide and methane sink in
617 wetland sediments under anoxic conditions. *Water Res* 2021;**194**:116958.

618 Coates JD, Achenbach LA. Microbial perchlorate reduction: rocket-fuelled metabolism. *Nat Rev*
619 *Microbiol* 2004;**2**:569–80.

620 Coates JD, Michaelidou U, Bruce RA *et al.* Ubiquity and Diversity of Dissimilatory
621 (Per)chlorate-Reducing Bacteria. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 1999;**65**:5234–41.

622 Cortés M, Avendaño P, Encalada O *et al.* Uncovering Hidden Microbial Diversity in
623 Nitrate/Iodide Deposits (NIDs) in the Domeyko District, Atacama Desert, Chile. *Soil Syst*
624 2024;**8**:46.

625 Das S. Critical review of water radiolysis processes, dissociation products, and possible impacts
626 on the local environment: A geochemist’s perspective. *Aust J Chem* 2013;**66**:522.

627 Dershwitz P, Bandow NL, Yang J *et al.* Oxygen Generation via Water Splitting by a Novel
628 Biogenic Metal Ion-Binding Compound. Parales RE (ed.). *Appl Environ Microbiol*
629 2021;**87**:1–14.

630 Edgar RC. MUSCLE: multiple sequence alignment with high accuracy and high throughput.
631 *Nucleic Acids Res* 2004;**32**:1792–7.

632 Elbon CE, Stewart FJ, Glass JB. Novel Alphaproteobacteria transcribe genes for nitric oxide
633 transformation at high levels in a marine oxygen-deficient zone. *Appl Environ Microbiol*
634 2024;**90**, DOI: 10.1128/aem.02099-23.

635 Ettwig KF, Butler MK, Le Paslier D *et al.* Nitrite-driven anaerobic methane oxidation by
636 oxygenic bacteria. *Nature* 2010;**464**:543–8.

637 Ettwig KF, Speth DR, Reimann J *et al.* Bacterial oxygen production in the dark. *Front Microbiol*
638 2012;**3**:273.

639 Fischer WW, Hemp J, Johnson JE. Evolution of Oxygenic Photosynthesis. *Annu Rev Earth*
640 *Planet Sci* 2016;**44**:647–83.

641 Garcia-Robledo E, Padilla CC, Aldunate M *et al.* Cryptic oxygen cycling in anoxic marine
642 zones. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 2017;**114**:8319–24.

643 Garcia HE, Gordon LI. Oxygen solubility in seawater: Better fitting equations. *Limnol Oceanogr*
644 1992;**37**:1307–12.

645 Gazitúa MC, Vik DR, Roux S *et al.* Potential virus-mediated nitrogen cycling in oxygen-
646 depleted oceanic waters. *ISME J* 2021;**15**:981–98.

647 van Ginkel CG, Rikken GB, Kroon AGM *et al.* Purification and characterization of chlorite
648 dismutase: a novel oxygen-generating enzyme. *Arch Microbiol* 1996;**166**:321–6.

649 Gomaa F, Utter DR, Powers C *et al.* Multiple integrated metabolic strategies allow foraminiferan
650 protists to thrive in anoxic marine sediments. *Sci Adv* 2021;**7**:1–13.

651 Graef C, Hestnes AG, Svenning MM *et al.* The active methanotrophic community in a wetland
652 from the High Arctic. *Environ Microbiol Rep* 2011;**3**:466–72.

653 Graf JS, Mayr MJ, Marchant HK *et al.* Bloom of a denitrifying methanotroph, ‘*Candidatus*
654 *Methylomirabilis limnetica*’, in a deep stratified lake. *Environ Microbiol* 2018;**20**:2598–
655 614.

656 Gutsalo LK. Radiolysis of water as the source of free oxygen in the underground hydrosphere.
657 *Geochemistry Int* 1971;**8**:897–903.

658 Hanke A, Berg J, Hargesheimer T *et al.* Selective Pressure of Temperature on Competition and
659 Cross-Feeding within Denitrifying and Fermentative Microbial Communities. *Front*
660 *Microbiol* 2016;**6**:1461.

661 Hayashi T, Obata H, Gamo T *et al.* Distribution and Phylogenetic Characteristics of the Genes
662 Encoding Enzymes Relevant to Methane Oxidation in Oxygen Minimum Zones of the
663 Eastern Pacific Ocean. *Res J Environ Sci* 2007;**6**:275–84.

664 He H, Wu X, Xian H *et al.* An abiotic source of Archean hydrogen peroxide and oxygen that
665 pre-dates oxygenic photosynthesis. *Nat Commun* 2021;**12**:6611.

666 He H, Wu X, Zhu J *et al.* A mineral-based origin of Earth’s initial hydrogen peroxide and
667 molecular oxygen. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 2023;**120**:e2221984120.

668 He R, Wang J, Pohlman JW *et al.* Metabolic flexibility of aerobic methanotrophs under anoxic
669 conditions in Arctic lake sediments. *ISME J* 2022;**16**:78–90.

670 He Z, Cai C, Wang J *et al.* A novel denitrifying methanotroph of the NC10 phylum and its
671 microcolony. *Sci Rep* 2016;**6**:32241.

672 Hedges SB, Blair JE, Venturi ML *et al.* A molecular timescale of eukaryote evolution and the

673 rise of complex multicellular life. *BMC Evol Biol* 2004;**4**:2.

674 Helman Y, Barkan E, Eisenstadt D *et al.* Fractionation of the Three Stable Oxygen Isotopes by
675 Oxygen-Producing and Oxygen-Consuming Reactions in Photosynthetic Organisms. *Plant*
676 *Physiol* 2005;**138**:2292–8.

677 Hemingway JD, Claire MW. Mass independent fractionation processes in the atmosphere.
678 *Treatise on Geochemistry*:in revision.

679 Hemingway JD, Goldberg ML, Sutherland KM *et al.* Theoretical estimates of sulfoxyanion
680 triple-oxygen equilibrium isotope effects and their implications. *Geochim Cosmochim Acta*
681 2022;**336**:353–71.

682 Hicks RJ, Fredrickson JK. Aerobic metabolic potential of microbial populations indigenous to
683 deep subsurface environments. *Geomicrobiol J* 1989;**7**:67–77.

684 Hirayama H, Suzuki Y, Abe M *et al.* Methylothermus subterraneus sp. nov., a moderately
685 thermophilic methanotroph isolated from a terrestrial subsurface hot aquifer. *Int J Syst Evol*
686 *Microbiol* 2011;**61**:2646–53.

687 Hofbauer S, Schaffner I, Furtmüller PG *et al.* Chlorite dismutases – a heme enzyme family for
688 use in bioremediation and generation of molecular oxygen. *Biotechnol J* 2014;**9**:461–73.

689 Hsu H-W, Postberg F, Sekine Y *et al.* Ongoing hydrothermal activities within Enceladus. *Nature*
690 2015;**519**:207–10.

691 Hu Q-Q, Zhou Z-C, Liu Y-F *et al.* High microbial diversity of the nitric oxide dismutation
692 reaction revealed by PCR amplification and analysis of the nod gene. *Int Biodeterior*
693 *Biodegradation* 2019;**143**:104708.

694 Jackson WA, Böhlke JK, Andraski BJ *et al.* Global patterns and environmental controls of
695 perchlorate and nitrate co-occurrence in arid and semi-arid environments. *Geochim*
696 *Cosmochim Acta* 2015;**164**:502–22.

697 Jackson WA, Böhlke JK, Gu B *et al.* Isotopic Composition and Origin of Indigenous Natural
698 Perchlorate and Co-Occurring Nitrate in the Southwestern United States. *Environ Sci*
699 *Technol* 2010;**44**:4869–76.

700 Johnson CG, Galy V V. Helium-flushed sheathed nickel tube reactor for continuous flow oxygen
701 stable isotope compound-specific analysis. *Rapid Commun Mass Spectrom* 2022;**36**:1–13.

702 Jørgensen BB. Bacteria and Marine Biogeochemistry. In: Schulz HD, Zabel M (eds.). *Marine*
703 *Geochemistry*. Berlin/Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag, 2006, 169–206.

704 Kalvelage T, Lavik G, Jensen MM *et al.* Aerobic Microbial Respiration In Oceanic Oxygen
705 Minimum Zones. Quan Z-X (ed.). *PLoS One* 2015;**10**:e0133526.

706 Kalyuzhnaya MG, Khmelenina VN, Kotelnikova S *et al.* Methylomonas scandinavica sp.nov., a
707 New Methanotrophic Psychrotrophic Bacterium isolated from Deep Igneous Rock Ground
708 Water of Sweden. *Syst Appl Microbiol* 1999;**22**:565–72.

709 Kietäväinen R, Purkamo L. The origin, source, and cycling of methane in deep crystalline rock
710 biosphere. *Front Microbiol* 2015;**6**:725.

711 Knox M, Quay PD, Wilbur D. Kinetic isotopic fractionation during air-water gas transfer of O₂,
712 N₂, CH₄, and H₂. *J Geophys Res Ocean* 1992;**97**:20335–43.

713 Kounaves SP, Carrier BL, O’Neil GD *et al.* Evidence of martian perchlorate, chlorate, and
714 nitrate in Mars meteorite EETA79001: Implications for oxidants and organics. *Icarus*
715 2014;**229**:206–13.

716 Kraft B, Jehmlich N, Larsen M *et al.* Oxygen and nitrogen production by an ammonia-oxidizing
717 archaeon. *Science* 2022;**375**:97–100.

718 Kuloyo O, Ruff SE, Cahill A *et al.* Methane oxidation and methylotroph population dynamics in

719 groundwater mesocosms. *Environ Microbiol* 2020;**22**:1222–37.

720 Larsen M, Lehner P, Borisov SM *et al.* In situ quantification of ultra-low O₂ concentrations in
721 oxygen minimum zones: Application of novel optodes. *Limnol Oceanogr Methods*
722 2016;**14**:784–800.

723 Lee AQ, Streit BR, Zdilla MJ *et al.* Mechanism of and exquisite selectivity for O–O bond
724 formation by the heme-dependent chlorite dismutase. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 2008;**105**:15654–
725 9.

726 Lehner P, Larndorfer C, Garcia-Robledo E *et al.* LUMOS - A Sensitive and Reliable Optode
727 System for Measuring Dissolved Oxygen in the Nanomolar Range. *PLoS One*
728 2015;**10**:e0128125.

729 Li B, Yeung LY, Hu H *et al.* Kinetic and equilibrium fractionation of O₂ isotopologues during
730 air-water gas transfer and implications for tracing oxygen cycling in the ocean. *Mar Chem*
731 2019;**210**:61–71.

732 Lichtenberg M, Line L, Schrameyer V *et al.* Nitric-oxide-driven oxygen release in anoxic
733 *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *iScience* 2021;**24**:103404.

734 Lösekann T, Knittel K, Nadalig T *et al.* Diversity and Abundance of Aerobic and Anaerobic
735 Methane Oxidizers at the Haakon Mosby Mud Volcano, Barents Sea. *Appl Environ*
736 *Microbiol* 2007;**73**:3348–62.

737 Lv S, Zheng F, Wang Z *et al.* Unveiling novel pathways and key contributors in the nitrogen
738 cycle: Validation of enrichment and taxonomic characterization of oxygenic denitrifying
739 microorganisms in environmental samples. *Sci Total Environ* 2024;**908**:168339.

740 Mader M, Schmidt C, van Geldern R *et al.* Dissolved oxygen in water and its stable isotope
741 effects: A review. *Chem Geol* 2017;**473**:10–21.

742 Maixner F, Wagner M, Lückner S *et al.* Environmental genomics reveals a functional chlorite
743 dismutase in the nitrite-oxidizing bacterium ‘Candidatus Nitrospira defluvii.’ *Environ*
744 *Microbiol* 2008;**10**:3043–56.

745 Martin PE, Farley KA, Archer PD *et al.* Reevaluation of Perchlorate in Gale Crater Rocks
746 Suggests Geologically Recent Perchlorate Addition. *J Geophys Res Planets* 2020;**125**:1–15.

747 Martinez-Cruz K, Leewis M-C, Herriott IC *et al.* Anaerobic oxidation of methane by aerobic
748 methanotrophs in sub-Arctic lake sediments. *Sci Total Environ* 2017;**607–608**:23–31.

749 Mehboob F, Wolterink AFM, Vermeulen AJ *et al.* Purification and characterization of a chlorite
750 dismutase from *Pseudomonas chloritidismutans*. *FEMS Microbiol Lett* 2009;**293**:115–21.

751 Michalski JR, Onstott TC, Mojzsis SJ *et al.* The Martian subsurface as a potential window into
752 the origin of life. *Nat Geosci* 2018;**11**:21–6.

753 Mills CT, Amano Y, Slater GF *et al.* Microbial carbon cycling in oligotrophic regional aquifers
754 near the Tono Uranium Mine, Japan as inferred from $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\Delta^{14}\text{C}$ values of in situ
755 phospholipid fatty acids and carbon sources. *Geochim Cosmochim Acta* 2010;**74**:3785–805.

756 Minh BQ, Schmidt HA, Chernomor O *et al.* IQ-TREE 2: New Models and Efficient Methods for
757 Phylogenetic Inference in the Genomic Era. Teeling E (ed.). *Mol Biol Evol* 2020;**37**:1530–4.

758 Mlynek G, Sjöblom B, Kostan J *et al.* Unexpected Diversity of Chlorite Dismutases: a
759 Catalytically Efficient Dimeric Enzyme from *Nitrobacter winogradskyi*. *J Bacteriol*
760 2011;**193**:2408–17.

761 Momper L, Casar CP, Osburn MR. A metagenomic view of novel microbial and metabolic
762 diversity found within the deep terrestrial biosphere at <sc>DeMMO: A</sc> microbial
763 observatory in <sc>South Dakota</sc> , <sc>USA</sc>. *Environ Microbiol*
764 2023:2021.05.06.442964.

765 Morris RL, Schmidt TM. Shallow breathing: bacterial life at low O₂. *Nat Rev Microbiol*
766 2013;**11**:205–12.

767 Mosley OE, Gios E, Close M *et al*. Nitrogen cycling and microbial cooperation in the terrestrial
768 subsurface. *ISME J* 2022;**16**:2561–73.

769 Murali R, Hemp J, Gennis RB. Evolution of quinol oxidation within the heme-copper
770 oxidoreductase superfamily. *Biochim Biophys Acta - Bioenerg* 2022;**1863**:148907.

771 Nelson N, Ben-Shem A. The complex architecture of oxygenic photosynthesis. *Nat Rev Mol Cell*
772 *Biol* 2004;**5**:971–82.

773 Nisson DM, Kieft TL, Drake H *et al*. Hydrogeochemical and isotopic signatures elucidate deep
774 subsurface hypersaline brine formation through radiolysis driven water-rock interaction.
775 *Geochim Cosmochim Acta* 2023;**340**:65–84.

776 Oba Y, Poulson SR. Oxygen isotope fractionation of dissolved oxygen during reduction by
777 ferrous iron. *Geochim Cosmochim Acta* 2009a;**73**:13–24.

778 Oba Y, Poulson SR. Oxygen isotope fractionation of dissolved oxygen during abiological
779 reduction by aqueous sulfide. *Chem Geol* 2009b;**268**:226–32.

780 Oswald K, Milucka J, Brand A *et al*. Aerobic gammaproteobacterial methanotrophs mitigate
781 methane emissions from oxic and anoxic lake waters. *Limnol Oceanogr* 2016;**61**:S101–18.

782 Padilla CC, Bertagnolli AD, Bristow LA *et al*. Metagenomic Binning Recovers a
783 Transcriptionally Active Gammaproteobacterium Linking Methanotrophy to Partial
784 Denitrification in an Anoxic Oxygen Minimum Zone. *Front Mar Sci* 2017;**4**:23.

785 Padilla CC, Bristow LA, Sarode N *et al*. NC10 bacteria in marine oxygen minimum zones. *ISME*
786 *J* 2016;**10**:2067–71.

787 Parker SR, Darvis MN, Poulson SR *et al*. Dissolved oxygen and dissolved inorganic carbon
788 stable isotope composition and concentration fluxes across several shallow floodplain
789 aquifers and in a diffusion experiment. *Biogeochemistry* 2014;**117**:539–52.

790 Parker SR, Gammons CH, Garrett Smith M *et al*. Behavior of stable isotopes of dissolved
791 oxygen, dissolved inorganic carbon and nitrate in groundwater at a former wood treatment
792 facility containing hydrocarbon contamination. *Appl Geochemistry* 2012;**27**:1101–10.

793 Parks DH, Chuvochina M, Rinke C *et al*. GTDB: an ongoing census of bacterial and archaeal
794 diversity through a phylogenetically consistent, rank normalized and complete genome-
795 based taxonomy. *Nucleic Acids Res* 2022;**50**:785–94.

796 Pytlak A, Stępniewska Z, Kuźniar A *et al*. Potential for Aerobic Methane Oxidation in
797 Carboniferous Coal Measures. *Geomicrobiol J* 2014;**31**:737–47.

798 Rajala P, Bomberg M, Kietäväinen R *et al*. Rapid Reactivation of Deep Subsurface Microbes in
799 the Presence of C-1 Compounds. *Microorganisms* 2015;**3**:17–33.

800 Reis PCJ, Tsuji JM, Weiblen C *et al*. Enigmatic persistence of aerobic methanotrophs in oxygen-
801 limiting freshwater habitats. *ISME J* 2024;**1675**:1–26.

802 Révész K, Böhlke J-K, Smith RL *et al*. $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ composition of dissolved O₂ undergoing
803 respiration in contaminated ground water. *IAEA Tech Rep* 1999;**361**:281–2.

804 Rissanen A, Saarenheimo J, Tirola M *et al*. Gammaproteobacterial methanotrophs dominate
805 methanotrophy in aerobic and anaerobic layers of boreal lake waters. *Aquat Microb Ecol*
806 2018;**81**:257–76.

807 Ronen D, Magaritz M, Almon E *et al*. Anthropogenic anoxification (“eutrophication”) of the
808 water table region of a deep phreatic aquifer. *Water Resour Res* 1987;**23**:1554–60.

809 Ruff SE. Microbial Communities and Metabolisms at Hydrocarbon Seeps. In: Teske AP,
810 Carvalho V (eds.). *Marine Hydrocarbon Seeps - Microbiology and Biogeochemistry of a*

811 *Global Marine Habitat*. Springer Oceanography, 2020, 1–19.

812 Ruff SE, Arnds J, Knittel K *et al*. Microbial Communities of Deep-Sea Methane Seeps at
813 Hikurangi Continental Margin (New Zealand). Stal LJ (ed.). *PLoS One* 2013;**8**:e72627.

814 Ruff SE, Biddle JF, Teske AP *et al*. Global dispersion and local diversification of the methane
815 seep microbiome. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2015;**112**:4015–20.

816 Ruff SE, Felden J, Gruber-Vodicka HR *et al*. In situ development of a methanotrophic
817 microbiome in deep-sea sediments. *ISME J* 2019;**13**:197–213.

818 Ruff SE, Hrabe de Angelis I, Mullis M *et al*. A global atlas of subsurface microbiomes reveals
819 phylogenetic novelty, large scale biodiversity gradients, and a marine-terrestrial divide.
820 *BioRxiv* 2024, DOI: 10.1101/2024.04.29.591682.

821 Ruff SE, Humez P, de Angelis IH *et al*. Hydrogen and dark oxygen drive microbial productivity
822 in diverse groundwater ecosystems. *Nat Commun* 2023;**14**:3194.

823 Sarkar J, Mondal M, Bhattacharya S *et al*. Extremely oligotrophic and complex-carbon-
824 degrading microaerobic bacteria from Arabian Sea oxygen minimum zone sediments. *Arch*
825 *Microbiol* 2024;**206**:179.

826 Schaffner I, Hofbauer S, Krutzler M *et al*. Mechanism of chlorite degradation to chloride and
827 dioxygen by the enzyme chlorite dismutase. *Arch Biochem Biophys* 2015;**574**:18–26.

828 Schaffner I, Mlynek G, Flego N *et al*. Molecular Mechanism of Enzymatic Chlorite
829 Detoxification: Insights from Structural and Kinetic Studies. *ACS Catal* 2017;**7**:7962–76.

830 Sharp ZD, Wostbrock JAG, Pack A. Mass-dependent triple oxygen isotope variations in
831 terrestrial materials. *Geochemical Perspect Lett* 2018;**7**:27–31.

832 Shen J, Zerkle AL, Stueeken E *et al*. Nitrates as a Potential N Supply for Microbial Ecosystems
833 in a Hyperarid Mars Analog System. *Life* 2019;**9**:79.

834 Smith MG, Parker SR, Gammons CH *et al*. Tracing dissolved O₂ and dissolved inorganic carbon
835 stable isotope dynamics in the Nyack aquifer: Middle Fork Flathead River, Montana, USA.
836 *Geochim Cosmochim Acta* 2011;**75**:5971–86.

837 Smith ML, Claire MW, Catling DC *et al*. The formation of sulfate, nitrate and perchlorate salts
838 in the martian atmosphere. *Icarus* 2014;**231**:51–64.

839 Song M, Warr O, Telling J *et al*. Hydrogeological controls on microbial activity and habitability
840 in the Precambrian continental crust. *Geobiology* 2024;**22**:1–19.

841 Stepniewska Z, Pytlak A, Kuźniar A. Methanotrophic activity in Carboniferous coalbed rocks.
842 *Int J Coal Geol* 2013;**106**:1–10.

843 Stepniewska Z, Pytlak A, Kuźniar A. Distribution of the methanotrophic bacteria in the Western
844 part of the Upper Silesian Coal Basin (Borynia-Zofiówka and Budryk coal mines). *Int J*
845 *Coal Geol* 2014;**130**:70–8.

846 Stern JC, Sutter B, Freissinet C *et al*. Evidence for indigenous nitrogen in sedimentary and
847 aeolian deposits from the Curiosity rover investigations at Gale crater, Mars. *Proc Natl*
848 *Acad Sci U S A* 2015;**112**:4245–50.

849 Stolper DA, Fischer WW, Bender ML. Effects of temperature and carbon source on the isotopic
850 fractionations associated with O₂ respiration for 17O/16O and 18O/16O ratios in *E. coli*.
851 *Geochim Cosmochim Acta* 2018;**240**:152–72.

852 Stone J, Edgar JO, Gould JA *et al*. Tectonically-driven oxidant production in the hot biosphere.
853 *Nat Commun* 2022;**13**:4529.

854 Sturchio NC, Caffee M, Beloso AD *et al*. Chlorine-36 as a Tracer of Perchlorate Origin. *Environ*
855 *Sci Technol* 2009;**43**:6934–8.

856 Sutherland KM, Hemingway JD, Johnston DT. The influence of reactive oxygen species on

857 “respiration” isotope effects. *Geochim Cosmochim Acta* 2022;**324**:86–101.

858 Sutherland KM, Johnston DT, Hemingway JD *et al.* Revised microbial and photochemical triple-
859 oxygen isotope effects improve marine gross oxygen production estimates. *PNAS Nexus*
860 2022;**1**:1–11.

861 Tavormina PL, Ussler W, Steele JA *et al.* Abundance and distribution of diverse membrane-
862 bound monooxygenase (Cu-MMO) genes within the Costa Rica oxygen minimum zone.
863 *Environ Microbiol Rep* 2013;**5**:414–23.

864 Tiano L, Garcia-Robledo E, Dalsgaard T *et al.* Oxygen distribution and aerobic respiration in the
865 north and south eastern tropical Pacific oxygen minimum zones. *Deep Sea Res Part I*
866 *Oceanogr Res Pap* 2014;**94**:173–83.

867 Tiano L, Garcia-Robledo E, Revsbech NP. A New Highly Sensitive Method to Assess
868 Respiration Rates and Kinetics of Natural Planktonic Communities by Use of the
869 Switchable Trace Oxygen Sensor and Reduced Oxygen Concentrations. *PLoS One*
870 2014;**9**:e105399.

871 Versantvoort W, Guerrero-Cruz S, Speth DR *et al.* Comparative Genomics of Candidatus
872 Methyloirabilis Species and Description of Ca. Methyloirabilis Lanthanidiphila. *Front*
873 *Microbiol* 2018;**9**:1–10.

874 Waite JH, Glein CR, Perryman RS *et al.* Cassini finds molecular hydrogen in the Enceladus
875 plume: Evidence for hydrothermal processes. *Science* 2017;**356**:155–9.

876 Walvoord MA, Phillips FM, Stonestrom DA *et al.* A Reservoir of Nitrate Beneath Desert Soils.
877 *Science* 2003;**302**:1021–4.

878 Wassenaar LI, Hendry MJ. Dynamics and Stable Isotope Composition of Gaseous and Dissolved
879 Oxygen. *Ground Water* 2007;**45**:447–60.

880 Weelink SAB, Tan NCG, Ten Broeke H *et al.* Physiological and phylogenetic characterization of
881 a stable benzene-degrading, chlorate-reducing microbial community. *FEMS Microbiol Ecol*
882 2007;**60**:312–21.

883 Winograd IJ, Robertson FN. Deep oxygenated ground water: Anomaly or common occurrence?
884 *Science* 1982;**216**:1227–30.

885 Wostbrock JAG, Cano EJ, Sharp ZD. An internally consistent triple oxygen isotope calibration
886 of standards for silicates, carbonates and air relative to VSMOW2 and SLAP2. *Chem Geol*
887 2020;**533**:119432.

888 Wu ML, Ettwig KF, Jetten MSM *et al.* A new intra-aerobic metabolism in the nitrite-dependent
889 anaerobic methane-oxidizing bacterium Candidatus ‘Methyloirabilis oxyfera.’ *Biochem*
890 *Soc Trans* 2011;**39**:243–8.

891 Xu J, Logan BE. Measurement of chlorite dismutase activities in perchlorate respiring bacteria. *J*
892 *Microbiol Methods* 2003;**54**:239–47.

893 Xu J, Sahai N, Eggleston CM *et al.* Reactive oxygen species at the oxide/water interface:
894 Formation mechanisms and implications for prebiotic chemistry and the origin of life. *Earth*
895 *Planet Sci Lett* 2013;**363**:156–67.

896 Yun J, Ma A, Li Y *et al.* Diversity of methanotrophs in Zoige wetland soils under both anaerobic
897 and aerobic conditions. *J Environ Sci* 2010;**22**:1232–8.

898 Zedelius J, Rabus R, Grundmann O *et al.* Alkane degradation under anoxic conditions by a
899 nitrate-reducing bacterium with possible involvement of the electron acceptor in substrate
900 activation. *Environ Microbiol Rep* 2011;**3**:125–35.

901 Zeng X, Alain K, Shao Z. Microorganisms from deep-sea hydrothermal vents. *Mar Life Sci*
902 *Technol* 2021;**3**:204–30.

903 Zhang Y, Ma A, Liu W *et al.* The Occurrence of Putative Nitric Oxide Dismutase (Nod) in an
904 Alpine Wetland with a New Dominant Subcluster and the Potential Ability for a Methane
905 Sink. *Archaea* 2018;**2018**:1–7.

906 Zhu B, Bradford L, Huang S *et al.* Unexpected Diversity and High Abundance of Putative Nitric
907 Oxide Dismutase (Nod) Genes in Contaminated Aquifers and Wastewater Treatment
908 Systems. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 2017;**83**:e02750-16.

909 Zhu B, Karwautz C, Andrei S *et al.* A novel Methylomirabilota methanotroph potentially couples
910 methane oxidation to iodate reduction. *mLife* 2022;**1**:323–8.

911 Zhu B, Wang J, Bradford LM *et al.* Nitric Oxide Dismutase (nod) Genes as a Functional Marker
912 for the Diversity and Phylogeny of Methane-Driven Oxygenic Denitrifiers. *Front Microbiol*
913 2019;**10**:1577.

914 Zhu B, Wang Z, Kanaparthi D *et al.* Long-Read Amplicon Sequencing of Nitric Oxide
915 Dismutase (nod) Genes Reveal Diverse Oxygenic Denitrifiers in Agricultural Soils and
916 Lake Sediments. *Microb Ecol* 2020;**80**:243–7.

917 Zimorski V, Mentel M, Tielens AGM *et al.* Energy metabolism in anaerobic eukaryotes and
918 Earth’s late oxygenation. *Free Radic Biol Med* 2019;**140**:279–94.

919